

MODELING OF NON-ISOTHERMAL LIQUID COMPOSITE MOLDING: THE HEAT DISPERSION ISSUE

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Keywords: *Liquid Composite Molding, Process Simulation, Heat Transfer*

1 Introduction

In liquid composite molding, the injected resin has to saturate the dry fibrous reinforcement bed within the mold cavity. The resin flow patterns depend on the infusion scheme – such as gate and vent location or pre-heating – and it will determine the process time and part quality. As the flow patterns may be hard to estimate, the flow modeling has been developed and is commonly used to verify the injection schemes [1-5]. Models can be also used to optimize the process or to deal with the process variability through process control [6-8].

The simulation process has been well refined for isothermal modeling. The efficiency of the numerical algorithms permits one to run hundreds of simulations in a very short time to address the expected variations, optimize the process and even introduce model based on line control [9].

In the case of non-isothermal process – whether the resin reacts or not – the numerical approach is well established [4,10-11], but the simulation techniques are far less efficient. Obviously, there are cases in which the temperature in mold varies with location and may accelerate curing reaction. The resin viscosity may vary significantly with the temperature and cure state, and thus the non-isothermal model is needed.

To determine the temperature and cure field, heat transfer and cure field equations are coupled with the mass conservation, resulting in more complex, non-linear system to solve.

Second factor to consider is that unlike the flow process, which is conveniently confined by the mold

or bag, the heat transfer may be coupled with the heat exchange with the mold and the environment which is in effect both before the filling starts and after it is completed as well.

All these issues pose obvious numerical and implementation challenges, but the difficulty is compounded by fundamental questions surrounding the modeling of energy and reaction equations [12]. This paper addresses one such issue: the effects of heat dispersion on temperature and temperature dependent flow field within the porous media.

This work will attempt to address three questions. First of them is how the model of heat dispersion – or the absence of thereof - influences the predicted temperature profiles. Second one is how can one experimentally characterize the heat dispersion behavior [13]. The numerical analysis of the experimental process offers us valuable insight (and supports the opinions of our reviewers). Lastly, does the behavior of our filling and cure change significantly in our numerical simulation with and without the heat dispersion model.

2. Heat Dispersion Evaluation

Traditionally, the heat transfer within the liquid in motion is separated into conductive and convective parts. For flow in porous media this separation is blurred by the fact that the flow velocity used in computation is the volume averaged value. Local velocity deviations due to the undulating path are not determined, as they do not contribute to the global mass transfer. However, they may still

influence the local heat transfer and temperature field.

Heat dispersion can be broadly divided into two parts: molecular dispersion which is generated by the random motion of the molecules in the resin (negligible in this case), and hydrodynamic dispersion which is due to the resin flow path through the complex shape of the pore space in the media at the microscopic level [14].

Figure 1: Experimental setup and schematics to determine heat dispersion.

The inclusion of heat dispersion in heat transfer model is accomplished through augmentation of effective thermal conductivity by a term dependent on (a) volume averaged resin flow velocity and (b) material properties and preform architecture [12]. Usually, only a rough estimate for the magnitude of this term is available and only for some components (this is a second order tensor).

We have previously established a method and

experimental setup to determine the relation between volume averaged flow velocity and heat dispersion for a given fabric reinforcement. There are also several available approximations of the dispersion coefficients. However, in practical computation the coefficients are often neglected.

In this paper we will model the flow/temperature field in two ways (i) heat dispersion will be neglected and only the conductive heat transfer with conductivity k_{eff} based on rule of mixtures will be considered and (ii) the effect of heat dispersion in the transverse direction will be included in the conductive term in the thickness direction. This heat dispersion term is given by the experimental results[]

$$K_{zz}/k_{eff} = 1.6219*Pe^{0.5215} + 1 \quad (1)$$

where the Peclet number Pe is defined as

$$Pe = (\langle u \rangle d_p) / (2\alpha_r (1 - v_f)) \quad (2)$$

using Darcy velocity $\langle u \rangle$, fiber diameter d_p , fiber volume fraction v_f and thermal diffusivity of fluid α_r . Note that if the velocity field is non-uniform, this coefficient will change with location.

3. Non-Isothermal Flow Modeling

The filling flow simulation for non-isothermal, reacting resin liquid composite molding is readily available, both commercially and through some research packages. Our analysis is carried with the simulation we developed called LIMS (Liquid Injection Molding Simulation). As shown in Figure 2, LIMS can model non-isothermal infusion, both in two- and three-dimensions. The access to LIMS source code allows us to adjust the constitutive equations for both the resin and the porous media. This allows us to implement or disable heat dispersion phenomenon and study the effect of the model on the final results and the simulation

accuracy.

Figure 2: Non-isothermal infusion into a cored panel.

Note that variable temperature field may have a profound impact on resin viscosity, and, consequently, on the flow field and filling times itself.

4. Numerical Implementation

Non-isothermal version of LIMS uses sequential solutions for flow, temperature and reaction. First, the pressure field is computed based on the current temperature field and flow advancement.

Then, new temperature is solved using finite element spatial discretization and implicit time-domain finite difference scheme. Next, the same approach is used to solve for new conversion (cure) if that is necessary. These steps are repeated at each time step. While this approach has the obvious advantage in limiting the problem size and offers some flexibility for adding cure models, several issues arise.

Most importantly, at the flow-front the temperature of control volumes being filled does not reflect the heat inertia of resin flowing into this volume. To alleviate the energy loss (or gain) rule of mixtures is applied at the flow-front to modify the temperature of freshly filled domain(s).

The second challenge that was addressed stemmed

from the need to evaluate the temperature before the filling starts and after the filling is completed and resin is allowed to continuously bleed out. As the CV/FEM approach computes time step based on filling a control volume, new algorithms were added to handle such a situation and provide reasonable time advancement even after the filling was completed. This, in turns would require one to handle thermal (and possibly cure) boundary condition at vent location, as the default (insulated) is not physical since energy is lost with outflow of resin.

Solution for this issue was found by generating an automatic heat flux boundary condition based on outflow, though this approach remains under investigation.

5. The Modeled Experiment

As stated above, one of the reasons for this work has been the analysis of an existing experimental technique. This consists of a preform placed in an insulated mold and infused by simulated resin, glycerin. The mold is heated by electric blanket from below. Temperature field is measured in time and dispersion coefficient is fitted to provide the best approximation of the temperature field [13].

Figure 3: Model of experimental infusion: dimensions and boundary conditions.

The dimensions of the mold cavity are 0.711 m in

length, 0.3048 m in width and thickness of 0.008 m. While the experiment has been run with two fabrics at different fiber volume fractions, for modeling we use only glass fabric with fiber volume fraction of 0.5 and permeability of 5.0×10^{-11} in-plane and 2.85×10^{-12} through-the thickness. The heat transfer coefficient of $6.29 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ is prescribed on the upper surface. The bottom surface is set to constant temperature of 350 K, as the constant heat flux used in actual experiment proved to small to obtain reasonable temperature gradients within the part for some process settings. Note that we applied these values directly to the preform, not through an aluminum plate as in the experiment [13]. The thermal properties of glass and glycerin are provided in Table 1 [13]:

Property	Units	E-Glass	Glycerin
Density (ρ)	kg/m^3	2560	1241
Heat Capacity (C_p)	J/kg.K	670	2512.7
Thermal Conductivity (k)	W/m.K	0.417	0.295

Figure 4: Viscosity of glycerin as a function of temperature.

Finally, while there is no reaction, glycerin viscosity changes significantly with temperature as shown in Figure 4 and the tabular values from [15] were implemented as a viscosity model using

interpolation in lookup table. The transverse heat dispersion coefficient was used as described by Equation (1) or switched off to quantify the effect of this term on the behavior. The reinforcement dimension d_p (Eq. (2)) was set to 0.140 mm as this value was used experimentally when Eq. (1) was obtained. If dispersion is off, the effective conductivity was computed entirely from the rule of mixtures.

Compared to the experiment and its numerical processing, the aluminum plates on top and bottom are not actually modeled, instead the boundary conditions are applied directly to the preform. However, the model can include the temperature dependent viscosity and takes into account the filling stage as well as the temperature field before the resin arrives. This proves very important, as the room temperature viscosity of glycerin is much higher and hence the filling takes much longer to fill. The results below (Figure 5) show filling patterns for injection pressure of 4 atm. The filling process still would take about 10 minutes. At this flow rate the heating of resin is not very high as the steady state temperature field below clearly demonstrates.

Figure 5: Filling patterns for experiment with infusion pressure of 4 atm. Dispersion is modeled by Eq. (1).

Figure 6: Temperature with heat dispersion (after 2000 s) with injection pressure of 4 atm..

For further analysis, two dimensional cross section models were used as they provide faster computation. Three-dimensional results clearly demonstrate – as a simple analysis would tell you - that the problem is actually two-dimensional only. The effects of meshing and convergence were only briefly investigated. The domain simplicity allows one to mesh it rather roughly, with 781 degrees of freedom. The refined meshes of 2961 and 6541 degrees of freedom were also tested. The flow patterns obtained by the 781 degree of freedom mesh, 2961 DOF mesh and 6541 DOF mesh are shown below in Figure 7. The convergence of fill time is fairly slow. The change between the coarse and medium mesh tops 10%. To optimize the simulation times and obtain reasonable results, the medium mesh was utilized in the further studies.

Figure 7: Flow patterns obtained for glycerin injected at 4 atm with 781, 2961 and 6541 degrees of freedom.

5. Results and Discussion

The influence of heat dispersion in a particular case is coupled with flow velocity which is in turn coupled through viscosity to temperature and, finally, to heat dispersion. It cannot be simply factored out from the equations, even for this problem. However, intuitively it should not be significant for low flow rates (as it varies proportionally with velocity). On the other hand, for high flow velocity the dispersion grows slower than the convective term (Eq. (1)) and one might expect the temperature profile to be convection-dominated. Whether - and where - the dispersion coefficient is important in the mid-range remains to be seen.

As we are most interested in the influence of heat dispersion on flow patterns and fill-time, we will map the relation between fill-time, injection pressure and the extent of resin viscosity dependence on temperature. To modify the later, we use a simple exponential model for viscosity:

$$\eta = \eta_0 \cdot e^{-b(T-T_0)} \quad (3)$$

As the temperature range within our numerical experiment is limited to 293 to 350 K, we can describe the viscosity variation by a simple ratio of

maximal and minimal viscosity $a = \eta_{max}/\eta_{min}$. Note that η_{max} is always set to 1 Pa.s in computations. This allows us to plot the fill time as a function of injection pressure (relative to atmospheric pressure) and the viscosity ratio.

To compare the effect of dispersion on the temperature distribution, we will compare the temperature contour plots with and without dispersion. For all the results, we plot the steady state temperature field.

For constant viscosity, the flow patterns do not change with temperature and with dispersion model, although the temperature field does change with dispersion. The fill time dependence on inlet pressure is straightforward (Figures 8 and 9).

Figure 8: Top two show the filling patterns and the temperature field that exclude dispersion (top) while the bottom two include the dispersion term Injection Pressure= 1 atm. $a=1$ (No viscosity dependence on temperature)

While the temperature change on upper surface is visible in contour plot, it is actually only on the order of 1 C for 1 atm injection pressure and 3 C for the 10 atm injection pressure with a temperature

range of 57 C, i.e., 2 and 6% respectively. This makes the effect of dispersion measurable but not very significant.

Figure 9: Top two show the filling patterns and the temperature field that exclude dispersion (top) while the bottom two include the dispersion term Injection Pressure= 10 atm. $a=1$ (No viscosity dependence on temperature)

When the resin viscosity depends on temperature, the flow and temperature field becomes coupled. Consequently, the presence of heat dispersion influences the flow/fill patterns and fill time. Intuitively, this will be more significant as the viscosity becomes more dependent on temperature. For the case of 5 atm injection pressure and viscosity changing by a factor of 2 (Figure 10), the fill time changes from 2905 s without dispersion model to 2788 s with it – about 4%. The temperature shift is, again, only a few degrees C and the flow patterns show no discernible change (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Filling patterns and temperature field excluding dispersion (top) and including dispersion term (bottom): Injection Pressure= 5 atm. $a=2$ (At 350 K the viscosity is half of that at 293 K).

Figure 11: Filling patterns and temperature field excluding dispersion (top) and including dispersion term (bottom): Injection Pressure= 5 atm. $a=5$ (At 350 K the viscosity is one fifth of that at 293 K).

As the viscosity temperature dependence increases, the change in fill time with and without dispersion becomes noticeable. For viscosity range of 5 (viscosity decreases five-fold in the range 293 to 350 K), the presence of dispersion in model will reduce the fill time from 1545 s to 1343 s (13 %) as shown in Figure 11, and for viscosity range of 10 (Figure 12) it will change from 1040 s to 814 s (21%)

Figure 12: Filling patterns and temperature field excluding dispersion (top) and including dispersion term (bottom): Injection Pressure= 5 atm. $a=10$ (At 350 K the viscosity is one fifth of that at 293 K).

In the latter case, the temperature difference at top plate will slightly increase, but the flow patterns still do not change significantly.

The most significant difference between solutions obviously occurs for highest viscosity dependence and highest injection pressure (and consequently flow velocity and Pe). In our set that case is one with injection pressure 10 atm and viscosity range of 10 (Figure 13). The fill time decreases by 28 %, the temperature at the top plate changes by about 6 K and the resin heating region is visibly reduced (Figure 13). The flow patterns are still not visibly

changed.

Figure 13: Filling patterns and temperature field excluding dispersion (top) and including dispersion term (bottom): Injection Pressure=10 atm. a=10 (At 350 K the viscosity is one fifth of that at 293 K).

The effect of dispersion factor on filling time can be easily tabulated and charted as a function of changing viscosity due to the temperature dependence and the injection pressure. The latter maps directly to flow velocity or Pe but it can vary locally as the viscosity depends on temperature, therefore the curves were plotted as a function of applied pressure (Figure 14). Throughout the examined range, the influence of dispersion increases fairly uniformly with inlet pressure/ fluid velocity and viscosity dependence on temperature. The Peclet number (Eq. 2) in chart legend is computed using “nominal” flow velocity (Eq. 4), as the number used to compute the actual dispersion varies locally with the flow velocity.

$$\langle u \rangle = (p_{in} * K) / (L * \eta_{max}) \quad (4)$$

Note that for realistic range of values there is no decrease of dispersion effects because of

“convection” dominated problem – for that one would need much larger flow velocity.

Figure 14: The change of filling time caused by the inclusion of dispersion term. Peclet numbers are computed using “nominal” flow velocity (Eq. (4)) and fiber tow size of 0.14 mm.

6. Conclusions

As far as the influence of heat dispersion coefficient on processing is concerned, the results suggests that, heat dispersion has relatively small effect on the temperature profile and virtually none on the filling flow patterns, even in cases when the change of filling time is significant.

For infusion modeling, the filling time and flow patterns are most important. There was no recorded effect on flow patterns in this study. The effect of dispersion model on filling time is small to moderate. The time reduction due to proper dispersion modeling may be of the order of 20-30%, similar to the order in the experimental error when measuring preform permeability. This suggests that the effect should be modeled, but, on the other hand, high fidelity description of this phenomenon is not extremely important.

The effects grow with Peclet number – though the values in Figure 14 are only for orientation – and with stronger dependence of viscosity on temperature within the expected range. For fluids with limited variation of viscosity within the expected temperature range the dispersion effect is insignificant. Similarly, for low Peclet numbers it is not important, but that is directly obvious from Eq.

(1).The results have some implications for experimental determination of the heat dispersion, as outlined above (Figure 1). The experimental analysis to determine heat dispersion coefficient depends on measuring and matching the temperature profile. The effect is limited, but still, the expected changes of temperature should be easily measurable. The temperature effect may be magnified by a selection of experimental fluid with large dependence of viscosity on temperature. In the case of glycerin, the viscosity range is actually larger than ten.

On the other hand, such a selection of experimental fluid requires a careful analysis of flow field within the preform as it may become strongly non-uniform.

7. Acknowledgement

Research was sponsored by the Army Research Laboratory and was accomplished under Cooperative Agreement Number W911NF-08-2-062. The views and conclusions contained in this document are those of the authors and should not be interpreted as representing the official policies, either expressed or implied, of the Army Research Laboratory or the U.S. Government. The U.S. Government is authorized to reproduce and distribute reprints for Government purposes notwithstanding any copyright notation herein.

8. References

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